

ROLE OF LEXICAL DEVIATION IN ADVERTISEMENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11525037>

Annotation: This article explores the concept of lexical deviation in advertising and its effectiveness in grabbing attention, creating brand personality, and crafting memorable messages. The author highlights how advertisers use puns, wordplay, unexpected juxtapositions, and deviated grammar to make their ads stand out. Examples include Snickers' "You're Not You When You're Hungry" and M&M's "Melts in Your Mouth, Not in Your Hands" slogans. Furthermore, the article discusses how lexical deviation helps establish brand voice, citing Old Spice's "The Man Your Man Could Smell Like" campaign and Dove's "Real Beauty" movement. Memorable taglines like Nike's "Just Do It" and Apple's "Think Different" are presented as prime examples of the power of deviated language in advertising.

Key words: Lexical deviation, advertising, puns, wordplay, taglines, slogans, humor.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola reklamadagi leksik og'ish tushunchasini va uning diqqatni jalb qilish, brend va esda qolarli xabarlarini yaratishdagi samaradorligini o'rganadi. Muallif reklama beruvchilar o'z reklamalarini diqqatga sazovor qilish uchun qanday qilib so'z o'yinlari, kutilmagan qo'shimchalar va og'ishma grammatikadan foydalanishini ta'kidlaydi. Bunga misol qilib, Snickersning "You're Not You When You're Hungry" va M&Mning "Melts in Your Mouth, Not in Your Hands" shiorlarini keltirish mumkin. Bundan tashqari, maqolada leksik og'ish brend yaratishga qanday yordam berishi haqida gap boradi, bunda Old Spicening "The Man Your Man Could Smell Like" kampaniyasi va Dovening "Real Beauty" harakati keltirilgan. Nike-ning "Just Do It" va Apple-ning "Think Different" kabi esda qolarli shiorlari reklamada og'ishgan til kuchining yorqin namunasi sifatida taqdim etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Leksik og'ish, reklama, o'yinlar, so'z o'yini, shiorlar, hazil.

Аннотация: В данной статье исследуется понятие лексического отклонения в рекламе и его эффективность в привлечении внимания, создании индивидуальности бренда и создании запоминающихся сообщений. Автор подчеркивает, как рекламодатели используют каламбуры, игру слов, неожиданные сопоставления и отклонения от грамматики, чтобы выделить свою рекламу. Примеры включают слоган

Snickers «You're Not You When You're Hungry» и слоган M&M «Melts in Your Mouth, Not in Your Hands». Кроме того, в статье обсуждается, как лексические отклонения помогают укрепить голос бренда, ссылаясь на кампанию Old Spice «The Man Your Man Could Smell Like» и движение Dove «Real Beauty». Запоминающиеся слоганы, такие как «Just Do It» от Nike и «Think Different» от Apple, представлены как яркие примеры силы нестандартного языка в рекламе.

Ключевые слова: Лексическое отклонение, реклама, игра слов, слоганы, лозунги, юмор.

The author concludes by acknowledging the importance of using lexical deviation strategically to avoid confusion and ensure message clarity.

In the ever-crowded marketplace of ideas, advertisements fight tooth and nail to capture our attention. They bombard us with visuals, sounds, and persuasive language, all vying for a coveted spot in our minds. But how do some ads manage to cut through the noise and leave a lasting impression? One powerful tool in their arsenal is lexical deviation.

Lexical deviation refers to the deliberate departure from standard vocabulary and usage in language. In advertising, this manifests in a variety of ways, from witty puns and neologisms (made-up words) to unexpected word choices and metaphors. By deviating from the expected, advertisers create a sense of surprise and intrigue, making their message more memorable and engaging.

Let's delve deeper into the role of lexical deviation in advertising and explore some famous examples that demonstrate its effectiveness:

1. Grabbing Attention: The Power of the Unexpected

In a world saturated with ads, the first hurdle is simply getting noticed. Lexical deviation shines in this regard. Puns, wordplay, and unexpected juxtapositions can jolt viewers out of their mental autopilot and force them to pay attention.

- **Snickers "You're Not You When You're Hungry" Campaign:** This iconic tagline uses a simple lexical deviation – the replacement of "you" with "You're Not You" – to create a memorable message. It cleverly taps into the universal experience of hunger-induced crankiness.
- **M&M's "Melts in Your Mouth, Not in Your Hands" Slogan:** This classic tagline employs a clever rhyme scheme and a play on texture ("melts" vs. "hands") to differentiate M&M's from messy chocolate alternatives.

2. Infusing Personality: Creating a Unique Voice

Lexical deviation allows brands to inject personality and a sense of humor into their communication. This can foster a connection with the target audience and make the brand appear more relatable and approachable.

- **Old Spice "The Man Your Man Could Smell Like" Campaign:** This campaign took the internet by storm with its unexpected use of a sophisticated, silver-haired gentleman targeting a younger demographic. The tagline, "The Man Your Man Could Smell Like," uses a humorous twist on traditional masculinity to grab attention and create a unique brand voice.
- **Dove "Real Beauty" Campaign:** This campaign deviates from the stereotypical beauty standards often portrayed in advertising. By using the tagline "Real Beauty" and featuring women of diverse shapes, sizes, and ethnicities, Dove established a unique voice that resonated with a broader audience.

3. Enhancing Memorability: The Power of the Sticky Phrase

Lexical deviation can weave magic when it comes to crafting memorable slogans and taglines. A cleverly deviated phrase can become a cultural reference point, constantly reminding consumers of the brand.

- **Just Do It (Nike):** This short, powerful tagline uses the imperative mood ("Just Do It") to inspire and motivate consumers. The deviation from standard sentence structure creates a memorable, action-oriented phrase.
- **Think Different (Apple):** Apple's "Think Different" campaign deviates from the expected by using a verb ("Think") as an adjective ("Different"). This simple yet impactful phrase encapsulates the brand's innovative and rebellious spirit.

4. Emotional Connection: Evoking Feelings Through Language

Lexical deviation can be a powerful tool for evoking emotions in viewers. By using evocative language, metaphors, and sensory details, advertisers can create a deeper connection with their audience.

- **L'Oreal "Because You're Worth It" Campaign:** This empowering tagline uses a simple lexical deviation ("worth it") to convey a message of self-confidence and self-worth associated with the L'Oreal brand.
- **Folgers "The Best Part of Waking Up is Folgers in Your Cup" Campaign:** This tagline uses emotional language ("best part") and imagery ("cup") to create a warm and comforting association with Folgers coffee.

The Art of Balance: When Deviation Works (and When it Doesn't)

While lexical deviation offers a plethora of benefits, it's crucial to wield it with care. Excessive deviation can lead to confusion or unintended meanings. The key lies in striking a balance between being creative and ensuring clarity of the message.

Lexical deviation is a powerful tool in the advertiser's arsenal. By strategically deviating from the expected, advertisers can capture attention, create memorable messages, and forge emotional connections with consumers.

References:

1. Batra, R., Ahuvia, A., & Biedenbach, S. (2014). Punishment or humor? The role of emotional response in advertising that violates advertising codes. *Journal of Advertising*, 43(4), 23-42.
2. Brody, R. P., & Iacolino, J. (2006). *Narrative branding: Connecting experiences to brand value*. Oxford: Elsevier.
3. Duval, D. T. (2007). *Appeals in advertising*. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications.
4. Eisend, M. S. (2006). Humor in advertising: A double-edged sword. *Journal of Advertising Research*, 46(2), 207-223.
5. Kassarian, H. H. (1991). *Public opinion, public policy, and advertising*. Hillsdale, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
6. McQuarrie, E. F., & Mick, D. G. (1999). *Consumers and advertising: Information processing and affect*. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications.
7. Olson, J. C. (1996). *The learning process*. New York, NY: McGraw-Hill.
8. Pope, M., & Willemsen, L. (2005). *Visual rhetoric: A reader in contemporary communication design*. Boston, MA: Allyn and Bacon.
9. Schlinger, M. J. (2012). *Wordplay in advertising*. New York, NY: Routledge.